

ORIGINAL RESEARCH PAPER

Education

AWARENESS ON HEALTH PROBLEMS DUE TO MOBILE PHONE USAGE AMONG ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

KEY WORDS: Awareness, Health Problem, Mobile Phone Usage

Dr. N. Subramanian

Principal, S Veerasamy Chettiar College of Education, Puliangudi – 627855, Tirunelveli, Tamilnadu.

Mrs. R. Parameswari*

M.Ed. IIF Year, S Veerasamy Chettiar College of Education, Puliangudi – 627855, Tirunelveli, Tamilnadu. *Corresponding Author

ABSTRACT

The main objective of the present study is to find out whether there is any significant difference between male and female arts and science college students in their Awareness on health problem due to mobile phone usage. The investigator used the survey method of research. Awareness on health problem due to mobile phone usage scale was developed and standardized by the investigator and the guide. The content validity of the tool was established by experts' opinion. The investigator used mean, standard deviation and t-test for analyzing the data. The investigator used the stratified random sampling technique. Ten Arts and science colleges were selected randomly from Arts and science colleges in Tirunelveli district. Thus the sample consists of 300 Arts and science college student. The investigator found the male higher secondary students have greater awareness on health problems due to mobile phone usage than their counter part.

INTRODUCTION

A mobile phone is wireless hand held device that can make and receive telephone calls over a radio link while moving around a wide geographic area. It does so by connecting to a cellular network provided by a mobile phone operator, allowing access to the public telephone network. In addition modern phones also support wide range variety of other services such as text messaging, MMS, E-mail, internet access, short range wireless communication, business application, gaming and photography. The very primary purpose of a mobile phone is that it provides a very easy alternative for communication. Mobile phones work as a great source of entertainment. In that sense mobile phones today have internet facilities. The mobile phones today have become a necessity, sure. But kids and teenager today become extensively addictive to these mobile phones. They tend to spend a huge chunk of their day on the mobile phones playing games, chatting and doing other things. These addictive habits lead to downfall in studies and performance which is one of the cons of the mobile phones today. Due to addictiveness of mobile phones, they lead to various health concerns among teenagers and adults. Long hours of exposures to the mobile phone screen lead to eye sight weakening. The glare from the screen of a mobile phone is harmful to the eyes. The continuous use of mobile phones for longer hours to talk on the call also causes other health problems such as headache. Mobile phone abuse is rising as an important issue among the world population including physical problems such as eye problems, muscular pain, and psychological problem such as tactile and auditory delusions. The radiation emitted by a mobile phone is not good for the mental health of a person. A very negative effect of mobile phone is this serious health concern.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out the level of awareness on health problems due to mobile phone usage among arts and science college students with respect to gender.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference between male and female arts and science college students in their Awareness on health problem due to mobile phone usage.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

- There is no significant difference between male and female arts and science college students in their Awareness on health problem due to mobile phone usage.

METHODOLOGY AND INSTRUMENTATION

The investigator used the survey method of research. Awareness on health problem due to mobile phone usage scale was developed and standardized by the investigator (Mrs. R. Parameswari) and the guide (Dr. N. Subramanian) 2018. The content validity of the tool was established by experts' opinion. Test-re-test method was followed for establishing the reliability of the tool. The investigator used mean, standard deviation and t-test for analyzing the data.

SAMPLE

The investigator used the stratified random sampling technique. Ten Arts and science colleges were selected randomly from Arts and science colleges in Tirunelveli district. Thus the sample consists of 300 Arts and science college students.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

Descriptive Analysis of Data:

Objective: To find out the level of awareness on health problems due to mobile phone usage among arts and science college students with respect to gender.

Table – 1: Table showing the level of awareness on health problems due to mobile phone usage among arts and science college students with respect to gender

Gender	Low		Average		High	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Female	12	11.2	71	66.4	24	22.4
	33	17.1	142	73.6	18	9.3

It is inferred from the above table that with regard to male, 11.2% of arts and science college students have Low level, 66.4% of student have average level and 22.4% of student have high level of awareness on health problems due to mobile phone usage. And also with regard to Female, 17.1% of students have low level, 73.6% of students have average level, and 9.3% of student have high level of Awareness on health problems due to mobile phone usage.

Inferential Analysis of Data:

Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between male and female arts and science college students in their Awareness on health problem due to mobile phone usage.

Table - 2: t-test showing the significance difference in awareness on health problems due to mobile phone usage among arts and science college students with respect to Gender

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	Calculated value	Table value	Remarks
Awareness on health problem due to mobile phone usage	Male	107	1.202	22.1	2.835	1.96	S*
	Female	193	1.128	20.7			

* Significant at 5% level of significant

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value (2.835) is greater than the table value (1.96) for df (298) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It indicates that there is significant difference in awareness on health problems due to mobile phone usage among arts and science college students with respect to gender.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

The investigator found from descriptive analysis of data that 66.4% of male arts and science college students have average level of awareness on health problems due to mobile phone usage. But 73.6% of female higher secondary students have average level of awareness on health problems due to mobile phone usage. And also the investigator got the result from t-test through inferential analysis that the male higher secondary students have greater awareness on health problems due to mobile phone usage than their counter part. 21st century youngsters have addiction to mobile phone usage, but were not aware on health problems due to mobile phone usage, as mobile phones have become an integral part of life. So government and NGO's may organize more awareness programmes on health problems due to mobile phone usage.

REFERENCES

1. Abhiman puri, & Shaikh Abdul Wahed Patel. (2017). A study of mobile phone Addiction and mental health among Adolescent Girls studying in various streams. IJIP, 5(1), 146-151. doi:10.25215/0501.099
2. Acharya, P., & Waghrey, D. (2013). A study on some psychological health effects of cell phone usage amongst college going students. International journal of medical research and health sciences, 2(3). Retrieved from <http://www.ljmrhs.com>
3. Choudhary, & Vijay. (2017). Study on health effects of mobile tower radiation on human beings. IRJET, 4(11). Retrieved from <https://www.irjet.net>
4. Sato, & Yamaguchi. (2017). Analysis of mobile phone use among young patients with brain tumors in japan. Bioelectromagnetics, 38(5), 349-355. doi:10.1002/bem22047
5. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5680647/>